

Oxidative coupling of thiols to disulfides with silver carbonate supported on celite under solvent-free conditions

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Abstract : The oxidations of organic compounds by silver carbonate supported on celite ($\text{Ag}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{celite}$) under solvent free conditions have been studied. Thiols undergo oxidative coupling reactions to give disulfides under air atmosphere at room temperature. Reaction occurs smoothly; yields are high to excellent and over oxidation do not happen.

Keywords : Thiols, disulfides, solvent-free, silver carbonate, celite.

Introduction

Conversion of thiols to disulfides without over oxidation in organic chemistry and biochemistry are important and interesting of between the different methods. That has been studied for many years. The disulfide bond formation is important in peptides and bioactive molecules¹. Oxidation of thiols proceed stepwise, giving disulfides initially, over oxidation of disulfides leads ultimately to sulfonic acids but several intermediates frequently can be obtained². What happens in any particular oxidation depends on the disulfides, oxidant, possible catalyst and solvent³.

In recent years, several reagents or reagent systems have presented ability of thiols coupling into disulfides such as $\text{I}_2/\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{graphite}$ ⁴, clay supported iron(III) nitrate (clayfen)⁵, calcium hypo chlorite/montmorillonite K10⁶, Fe^{III} ion exchanged montmorillonite⁷, molybdate sulfuric acid/sodium nitrite⁸, mono chloro poly(styrene hydantoin)⁹, tetra methyl ammonium fluoro chromate¹⁰, and $\text{O}_2/\text{manganese(III)}$ Schiff base complex¹¹, *N-tert-butyl-N-chloro cyanamide*¹², tripropyl ammonium fluoro chromate¹³, ethylene bis(*N*-methyl imidazolium) chloro chromate¹⁴ and iron(III) trifluoro acetate/air¹⁵.

Solvent-free organic reactions have drawn great interest, particularly from the view point of green chemistry, because harmful organic solvents are not involved in the production process¹⁶. However, no studies are known in literature exploiting silver carbonate on celite under solvent-free conditions.

Results and discussion

We hereby report that $\text{Ag}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{celite}$ under solvent-free conditions can be used to oxidize aliphatic as well as aromatic thiols to the corresponding disulfides under conditions solvent free (Scheme 1).

R : Aryl, Alkyl

Scheme 1

The oxidation is carried out by uniformly mixing of the reagent with thiol at room temperature under air atmosphere giving in high yields (Table 1). The attractive features of this supported reagent include in modified activity and simple reaction work-up to mere filtration and washing with solvent. Benzylic thiols were reacted easily and the corresponding disulfides were obtained in high yields in short period of time (entries 1–3 and 8, Table 1). Saturated linear cyclic mercaptans were also subjected to oxidation and yields and reaction times were satisfactory (entries 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, and 10, Table 1).

This supported reagent can be used for the generation of a variety of thiols from their corresponding disulfides under solvent-free conditions at room temperature and under air atmosphere in high to excellent yields (Table 1). Isolation of the product from this oxidation is

Table 1. Oxidative coupling of thiols to disulfides with silver carbonate on celite under solvent-free conditions in air atmosphere at room temperature

Entry	Reactant	Reaction time (h)	Product	Oxidant/ Substrate	Yield (%)	M.p. of product (°C)	Ref. for product
1	Ph	1	Ph-SS-Ph	1 : 1	98 ^a	60–61	18
2	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	2.25	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -SS-C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	1 : 1	98 ^a	72	19
3	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	0.33	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -SS-C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	1 : 1	89 ^a	44	19
4	PhCH ₂	3	PhCH ₂ -SS-CH ₂ Ph	1 : 1	90 ^a	72	19
5	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	3.3	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉ -SS-C ₄ H ₉ - <i>n</i>	1 : 1	90 ^b	Oil	19
6	<i>cyclo</i> -C ₆ H ₁₁	4	<i>cyclo</i> -C ₆ H ₁₁ -SS-C ₆ H ₁₁ - <i>cyclo</i>	1 : 1	90 ^b	Oil	19
7	HOCH ₂ CH ₂	1.2	HOCH ₂ CH ₂ -SS-CH ₂ CH ₂ OH	1 : 1	89	25	18
8	<i>p</i> -MeO-C ₆ H ₄	0.25	<i>p</i> -MeO-C ₆ H ₄ -OMe- <i>p</i>	1 : 1	95	44	20
9	<i>n</i> -C ₈ H ₁₇	3.2	<i>n</i> -C ₈ H ₁₇ -SS-C ₈ H ₁₇ - <i>n</i>	1 : 1	97 ^b	Oil	20
10	HOOCCH ₂	1.5	HOOCCH ₂ -SS-CH ₂ COOH	1 : 1	98 ^b	Oil	21

^aYields refers to isolated product. ^bYields are based on GC analyses.

remarkably simple and consists merely in filtrations to remove the spent reagent system, followed by evaporation of the solvent.

From the results above, we have presented a mild, catalytic and efficient method for oxidation of thiols to disulfides by using silver carbonate supported on celite, under solvent-free conditions. The present procedure could be attractive because of reduced pollution, to excellent yields, no waste production and mild conditions, and ease of purification.

Experimental

Material :

Chemicals were purchased from Merck and Fluka Companies. IR spectra were run on a Shimadzu IR-435 FTIR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR was run on Bruker Avance (DRX 500 MHz) and Bruker Ultra Shield (400 MHz). All yields refer to pure isolated products. Melting points were recorded on a Melting Point SMP1 apparatus in open capillary tubes. The progress of reaction was followed with TLC. All the products are known and were characterized by comparison of their spectra (IR, ¹H NMR), TLC and physical data with those reported in the literature.

Preparation of silver carbonate supported on celite :

Silver carbonate supported on celite is prepared by method Mckillop and Young¹⁷. Amount of silver carbonate supported on celite has measured by titration method. The reagent system thus prepared contained about 0.4 g

(1.5 mmol) of Ag₂CO₃ per gram.

General procedure for oxidative coupling of thiols to disulfides :

A mixture of the thiols (3 mmol) and Ag₂CO₃/celite (containing 3 mmol of silver carbonate) were uniformly mixed at room temperature for the period in dictated (Table 1). The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC (methanol/acetic acid, 5 : 1). After completion of the reaction the solids were collected by filtration and washed with acetonitrile. The filtrate is concentrated and redissolved in dichloromethane (or CHCl₃), washed with 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. Drying (MgSO₄) and evaporation of the organic layer gave the crude disulfide, which recrystallised from methanol to afford pure disulfide.

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